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Executive-Legislative Relations And Governance Trajectories In Nigeria: The Road Not Taken

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ABSTRACT

The challenges of contemporary governance in political societies have become increasingly urgent to address. Across the globe, weak governance manifests through social, economic, cultural, administrative, and political dimensions. In Nigeria, evidence abounds of a decline in democratic quality, particularly in executive–legislative relations, largely driven by power struggles and the competing influence of political elites. Since gaining independence from colonial rule on October 1, 1960, the Nigerian political landscape has been marred by persistent altercations, fueled by the relentless quest of the political class to outmaneuver one another in the struggle for power. These tensions became even more pronounced with the return to democratic governance in 1999. This study, therefore, explored executive–legislative relations and governance trajectories in Nigeria. Specifically, it examined conflicts of interest inherent in the relationship between the executive and the legislature, often regarded as traditional rivals in the post-colonial Nigerian state. Methodologically, the study adopted content analysis, given its theoretical orientation. The analysis was anchored on the Marxian theory of the state, which underscores how contestations and occasional cooperation between these arms of government reflect the struggle for institutional independence and the decentralization of state power along functional lines. In light of this, the study advocates for constructive cohabitation between the executive and the legislature, with the potential to foster a new relationship that transcends president–party or party–government alliances, thereby strengthening governance for the attainment of a just and stable society.

Keywords: Executive-legislative relations; Governance; Post-colonial state; Democracy

INTRODUCTION

In any democracy, cordial relationships among the three arms of government—the executive, legislature, and judiciary—are fundamental to maintaining the constitution and upholding the rule of law. Over the years, however, the character of these relationships has shifted considerably, influenced by both governance dynamics and broader societal changes. Effective governance and development in a democratic setting are best achieved through collective participation. Within this framework, the legislature plays a central role as a catalyst for socio-economic development. Its relevance is not only reflected in the quality of debates and deliberations in parliament but also in the execution of constituency projects such as roads, electricity, and industries that directly impact citizens' welfare.

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Modern democracy is anchored on the separation of powers among the executive, legislature, and judiciary. Stability and good governance can only be achieved when these arms cooperate and understand their complementary roles. The true essence of democracy lies in ensuring that government policies and programmes reflect the needs of the people while operating within the rule of law. Since the legislature is tasked with enacting laws and the executive is mandated to implement them, the legislature can rightly be described as the “soul and essence” of a democratic nation.

Globally, constitutional arrangements vary in the distribution of power between the executive and legislature. In presidential systems like that of the United States, the legislature wields significant authority, particularly in policymaking and budgeting, due to its independent electoral mandate. Conversely, under Westminster parliamentary systems, executive dominance is more pronounced since the executive emerges from and is politically tied to the legislature. Between these extremes lie hybrid forms such as semi-presidential systems (France, Korea), parliamentary republics (Germany, Italy), and non-Westminster parliamentary monarchies (Netherlands, Sweden) (Lienert, 2005).

Party systems also play a critical role in shaping executive-legislative dynamics. Strong two-party systems often limit legislative influence, as the legislature typically aligns with the executive's agenda. In parliamentary systems, however, a majority party can destabilize its own government by voting against the budget or major policies. Executives gain further leverage when national parties control legislative candidate selection, making lawmakers more loyal to party leaders than to their constituencies. On the other hand, weaker two-party systems or multiparty systems often enhance legislative bargaining power, as executives must negotiate with more independent actors to secure support for budgets and policies. Such negotiations may occur both within and outside formal legislative structures, thereby reinforcing legislative influence over executive decisions (Posner & Chung-Keun, 2007).

In Nigeria, the constitution distributes power horizontally between the executive and the National Assembly under a presidential system, while also organizing authority vertically across federal, state, and local levels. The federal government retains broader powers, especially in monetary policy, foreign affairs, and national security. States, however, lack independent constitutions, and the absence of state or local police—coupled with instances of presidentially declared states of emergency—further underscores the federal government's dominance (Watts, 1999).

The ultimate goal of any government is to ensure good governance, defined as the effective delivery of goods and services to both present and future generations while maintaining law and order. Democratic systems, with their inherent checks and balances, provide a more effective framework for achieving these goals compared to authoritarian regimes. Under civilian rule, where leaders are elected periodically to represent the people, efforts are often made to ensure that the material and moral benefits of democracy reach citizens. This forms the true hallmark of democratic governance.

Nigeria's democratic experience since May 1999 generated widespread optimism, particularly after the failures of successive military regimes that left industries and infrastructure in ruins. Much of the progress recorded under civilian governments has been attributed to the system of checks and balances between the executive and legislature. As the principal organ of lawmaking, the legislature not only sets the direction for policy but also serves as a watchdog over the other arms of government—especially the executive—ensuring that it remains accountable to the people.

Against this backdrop, the central thrust of this study is to examine the extent to which executive-legislative relations have shaped the quality of governance trajectories in Nigeria over the years. It specifically interrogates the roles of both arms in driving socio-economic development and evaluates how their interactions have influenced governance outcomes.

Conceptual and Theoretical Compass

According to Heywood (2007), the executive represents the irreducible core of government. Similarly, Laski (1992, cited in Oni, 2013) emphasizes its crucial role in state administration. He argues that in every democratic system, the executive performs three primary functions: first, to determine the final choice of policy for submission to the legislature; second, to ensure that public services implement such policies as intended; and third, to coordinate the activities of the various departments of state. In line with this, Puke (2007) identifies the executive as the organ responsible for providing responsible governance. Edosa and Azelama (1995) also describe the executive as the implementation arm of government, noting that throughout history, the making and enforcement of binding rules have been central to governance. They contend that while states have existed without distinct legislatures, it is virtually impossible to find a state without an executive. Heywood (2007) supports this view, asserting that political systems can function without constitutions, assemblies, or even judiciaries, but cannot survive without an executive to formulate and enforce policy.

Similarly, Anifowose (2008) defines the executive as the organ responsible for applying the authoritative rules and policies of society. By implementing constitutions, statutes, decrees, and treaties, the executive gives expression to the will of the state. He identifies two principal roles of the executive: a ceremonial role, performed by the Head of State, and the administrative role, exercised by the Head of Government. In parliamentary systems, these roles are carried out by different officials, while in presidential systems, they are performed by the same person.

In contrast, the legislature is considered indispensable to representative liberal democracy. Across nations, legislatures are known by different names: “Parliament” in Britain, “National Assembly” in Nigeria, and “Congress” in the United States (Abonyi, 2006; Heywood, 2007; Lafenwa, 2009). It is widely regarded as the people’s branch, whose central function is to articulate and represent the collective will of the populace (Bernick & Bernick, 2008; Okoosi-Simbine, 2010). Taiwo and Fajingbesi (2004) see it as the primary forum for representing the electorate. Lafenwa (2009) describes the legislature as an elected body vested with lawmaking powers, the authority to represent constituencies, and the responsibility of monitoring government. Okoosi-Simbine (2010) similarly conceptualizes it as a lawmaking, deliberative, and policy-influencing institution, often referred to as the First Estate of the Realm—the site of sovereignty and the true expression of the people’s will. Its authority therefore derives directly from the people, and must be exercised on their behalf.

Legislatures may be unicameral or bicameral. Bicameralism, practiced in countries such as Nigeria, France, and the United States, consists of two chambers. In Nigeria and the United States, for example, the National Assembly and Congress each comprise a Senate (Upper House) and House of Representatives (Lower House). While Nigeria initially operated a unicameral legislature under the 1954 Lyttleton Constitution, it adopted a bicameral structure at independence in 1960, which was retained in the 1979 and 1999 constitutions. The purpose of bicameralism is to balance representation: one chamber ensures equal representation of federating units while the other reflects broader national interests. This system reduces the likelihood of legislative capture by despots and ensures wider inclusion of diverse social groups (Abonyi, 2006).

The theoretical framework for this study is grounded in the Marxist theory of the state, which arose in opposition to liberal theory’s notion of the state as a neutral arbiter serving the collective good (Okolie, 2006). Marxist theorists, beginning with Lenin (1984), argue that the state is the product of irreconcilable class antagonisms. It reflects the interests of the dominant economic class, which also wields political power and exploits subordinate groups (Jakutowski, 1973). Building on this perspective, scholars such as Alavi (1973), Ekekwe (1985), Ake (1985), and Ibeanu (1998) apply the theory to the neo-colonial state,

contending that post-colonial states, including Nigeria, remain creations of imperialism. According to Ekekwe (1985), the post-colonial state rests on colonial foundations designed to facilitate capital accumulation by foreign bourgeoisie in alliance with domestic elites through the exploitation of local resources. Although ostensibly independent, the Nigerian state continues to serve the interests of imperialism, with local ruling classes aligning themselves with foreign capital.

Ake (1985) highlights the post-colonial state's lack of autonomy, noting that it is deeply embedded in class struggles and reflects the narrow interests of the ruling elite, often in collaboration with foreign capital. Consequently, the Nigerian state lacks the institutional independence to mediate conflicts effectively. Similarly, Ibeanu (1998) argues that the colonial state did not seek legitimacy but instead functioned as an instrument of domination. In the post-colonial era, this state apparatus was inherited by a pseudo-capitalist elite, who transformed it into a tool for private enrichment rather than public service. For Ibeanu, the enduring crisis of democracy in Nigeria stems from these structural deficiencies, which manifest in several ways:

- An excessive premium on power that turns politics into warfare rather than a process of negotiation and peaceful transfer.
- A weak sense of shared destiny among ethnic groups, leading to exclusive, zero-sum strategies of power.
- The absence of effective institutions to regulate political competition, often escalating contests into ethnic warfare and enabling military dominance.
- The persistence of authoritarianism and consensus politics, masking deep social divisions.
- The personalization of political authority by leaders who exploit the limitless power of the state (Ibeanu, 1998).

The Marxist perspective therefore suggests that the peculiarities of the post-colonial Nigerian state—its limited autonomy, dependence on imperialism, and capture by predatory elites—have hindered democratic consolidation, distorted development, and alienated the people.

Within this framework, the study examined executive–legislative relations and governance in Nigeria between 1999 and 2015. It argues that Nigeria's historical experience and the weak economic base of its ruling class have prevented the restructuring of its political institutions. Instead, colonial legacies of authoritarianism, economic dependency, and primitive capital accumulation have persisted, undermining nation-building and reinforcing authoritarian liberalism. The legislature, historically subordinated to the executive since colonial times (Awotokun, 1998; Lafenwa, 2009), has struggled to assert itself as an independent institution. For decades, military rule further weakened legislative capacity, reducing it to a mere appendage of the executive (Saliu & Muhammad, 2010).

The study concludes that Nigeria's presidential system has not produced the anticipated democratic order or political stability. This is less a consequence of institutional design than of the prevailing political culture, which drives elites to pursue power at all costs, often through violence and manipulation. As Omoweh (2012) observes, politics in Nigeria has become the dominant avenue for wealth accumulation, leading elites to fight fiercely to capture and retain state power. Consequently, executive–legislative relations remain fraught, undermining the prospects for good governance and democratic consolidation.

Executive-Legislative Relations and Governance Crisis: An Empirical Verification

Executive–legislative relations refer to the interactions and overall transactions between the executive and legislative branches at various levels of government. In Nigeria's presidential system, both arms are vested with distinct constitutional powers, yet collaboration is often necessary to ensure effective governance, harmonious inter-organ relations, and the independence of the legislature (Dudley, 1982; Fasagba, 2010, cited in Oni, 2013). Over the years, these relations have generated debates around issues of cooperation, conflict, dominance, and the implications of such dynamics (Oni, 2013).

Rockman (1983) identifies four key dimensions of executive–legislative relations: governance values and perspectives, the roles of major players and institutions, and legislative oversight of executive behavior. Ideally, the relationship between these branches should be cordial and functional, as both institutions are

ultimately tasked with ensuring state administration and safeguarding the welfare of citizens. In practice, however, the relationship is complex, oscillating between cooperation and conflict depending on prevailing political circumstances.

Nigeria's federal system replicates this relationship at both national and state levels. The President heads the executive at the federal level, while governors lead at the state level. Similarly, the National Assembly functions as the federal legislature, while each state has its own House of Assembly. Despite constitutional provisions, relations between the legislature and executive in Nigeria have often been characterized by suspicion, rivalry, and political acrimony (Aiyede, 2005; Nwannekanma & Ogbodo, 2010). Since the return to democracy in 1999, managing these relations has remained a persistent challenge (Abonyi, 2006).

A major source of friction arises from the extensive appointment powers of the executive, which create a patronage system dominated by presidential or gubernatorial loyalists. These appointees often defend government policies not out of patriotism, but out of political loyalty (Corduneanu-Huci, 2014). Consequently, the Fourth Republic has been marked by repeated clashes between the two arms of government (Ikoronye, 2005; Mba, 2007). For instance, early in Obasanjo's administration, the unilateral scrapping of the Petroleum Trust Fund (PTF) was perceived by the legislature as usurpation of its lawmaking authority. Similarly, controversies surrounding the Electoral Act 2001 and the ICPC Act 2000 highlighted recurring tensions between both branches (Ehwarieme, 2001; Ogunmupe & Phillips, 2002; Sanyaolu, 2002; Dunmoye, 2002).

Budgetary politics has been another battleground. Although the Constitution grants the executive the power to prepare the budget (Section 81, CFRN 1999), approval and appropriation rest with the legislature. This overlap has led to recurrent conflicts over fiscal management and oversight (Lewis, 2011). Obasanjo himself accused the National Assembly of abusing its oversight function, further deepening tensions (Eminue, 2008). Even after securing a second term, Obasanjo's government faced legislative resistance, as shown when the National Assembly overturned his veto on the ICPC Bill (Aiyede, 2008).

Under President Yar'Adua, relations initially seemed calmer due to his more restrained leadership style (Lewis, 2011). However, his failure to transmit a formal notice of medical leave to the legislature, as required under Section 145 of the Constitution, created a constitutional crisis that exposed the fragility of Nigeria's institutions. The "doctrine of necessity" was eventually invoked to resolve the impasse (Sagay, 2010; Oboh, 2010). Similarly, President Jonathan's tenure was marred by disputes, including debates over whether constitutional amendments required presidential assent (Okorie, 2010; Vanguard, 2010), and the 2012 fuel subsidy removal, which provoked nationwide protests and legislative threats of impeachment (Akpan, 2012; Ameh, 2012).

State-level politics has been equally volatile, with legislatures often dominated or manipulated by governors. This is facilitated by their control over candidate selection, staffing, and funding. Impeachments have frequently been used as tools of political vendetta, often in violation of constitutional requirements. Examples include the controversial removals of Governors Alamiyeseigha (Bayelsa), Ladoja (Oyo), Obi (Anambra), and Dariye (Plateau), many of which were later overturned by the courts but still underscored the abuse of impeachment powers (Owei, 2002; Lawan, 2010; Ogunmade, 2006; Onah, 2007; Olojede, 2008). These episodes often involved the complicity of local godfathers and the presidency, with the ruling PDP playing a central role in orchestrating outcomes (Ngamsa, 2007; Airahuobhor, 2007; Fagbadebo, 2010).

Overall, executive-legislative relations in Nigeria since 1999 have been marked more by conflict than cooperation. Prolonged military rule prior to 1999 weakened the legislature's institutional capacity, leaving it vulnerable to manipulation by the executive. The pattern of executive interference in legislative leadership further eroded legislative independence, threatening the consolidation of democracy. The persistence of prebendal politics, impunity, and disregard for constitutional principles has compounded governance failures (Bassey, 2006).

Theoretically, the separation of powers was designed to prevent the concentration of authority, with Montesquieu (1748) and Madison (1788) famously arguing that “power must check power.” In Nigeria, however, weak accountability mechanisms and elite-driven politics have undermined this principle, allowing public interest to be routinely sacrificed for private gain (Momodu & Matudi, 2013). Even when the executive and legislature are dominated by the same ruling party, conflicts of interest persist, as seen in Obasanjo’s role in the removal of multiple Senate Presidents and a House Speaker despite shared party affiliation.

In conclusion, the pattern of executive–legislative relations in Nigeria’s Fourth Republic reveals deep institutional weaknesses and a political culture that prioritizes elite competition over good governance. Instead of fostering collaboration for democratic consolidation, these relations have too often stalled policymaking, undermined accountability, and exacerbated governance crises (Momodu & Matudi, 2013).

Crisis of Confidence: Re-inventing Executive-Legislative Relations in Nigeria

Nigeria has enjoyed sixteen years of uninterrupted democratic governance since May 29, 1999, following a prolonged period of military rule and political domination that lasted from 1983 to 1999. Yet, the Fourth Republic (1999–present) has been consistently characterized by conflict-ridden relations between two key political institutions—the executive and the legislature—both at the federal and state levels. Frequently, these conflicts have generated political tension severe enough to stall governance, resulting in inactivity and low productivity in state institutions. Nonetheless, the relationship between the executive and the legislature remains central to the attainment of good governance (Momodu & Matudi, 2013).

In Nigeria’s presidential system, the relationship between the legislature and the executive is built on the principle of separation of powers, with each organ assigned distinct functions and personnel, balanced by a mechanism of checks and balances. With the return to civilian rule in 1999, these roles were clearly outlined in the 1999 Constitution, particularly in Sections 4 and 5. The effectiveness of the presidential system, however, depends largely on healthy and constructive executive–legislative interactions, underpinned by democratic values. While occasional friction between the two arms is inevitable given the institutional design of presidentialism, such conflicts can be healthy for democratic consolidation when they reflect efforts by each branch to assert its constitutional role.

The realization of genuine democratic governance in this system is closely tied to the legislature’s capacity to independently and vibrantly fulfill its mandate of representation, lawmaking, and oversight. When the legislature lacks the autonomy or political space to influence policy and check executive power, the quality of democracy deteriorates. Between 1999 and 2015, executive dominance and interference in legislative processes weakened the legislature’s role as a true representative of the people. In many instances, state and national assemblies served merely as instruments of executive authority, providing constitutional legitimacy for decisions rather than acting as independent actors. This inability to perform effective oversight and policymaking functions not only undermined governance but also threatened a regression from democracy toward authoritarianism.

Both the legislature and executive are indispensable institutions in a presidential democracy, tasked with delivering good governance and democratic dividends. The success of this task, however, depends on whether their interactions are cooperative or conflictual. In Nigeria’s Fourth Republic, these relations have been dominated by dysfunctional conflicts that have stalled policymaking and implementation, thereby hindering governance outcomes. More troubling is the persistence of a political culture rooted in impunity and disregard for the rule of law—legacies of military rule—that have fueled recurrent crises between the executive and the legislature. From 1999 to 2015, this culture of personal aggrandizement, patronage, and clientelism shaped political behavior in ways that undermined democratic consolidation and obstructed political development.

Executive–legislative relations during this period displayed both cooperative and conflictual tendencies. On the conflictual side, tensions surfaced as early as 2001, only two years into the Fourth Republic, when sharp disagreements between the National Assembly and the executive at the federal level became highly publicized (The Punch, 2001). Such conflicts were replicated at state and even local government levels,

often culminating in the impeachment of high-ranking officials, including speakers, deputy speakers, and governors (The Punch, 2007). On several occasions, these disputes escalated to the point where Nigerians feared that the democratic project itself was at risk due to the recklessness and self-interest of political elites.

In any democracy—whether presidential or parliamentary—a cordial and functional relationship between the executive and the legislature is essential for good governance. This is particularly true in presidential systems, which are structurally more prone to executive–legislative tensions and the potential risks of democratic breakdown. Although conflict is inevitable, it can also strengthen democratic practice when properly managed, as lessons are often drawn from the processes of resolution. However, such disputes must not be allowed to escalate unchecked; rather, they should be promptly and constructively resolved through institutional dialogue and respect for constitutional procedures. Ultimately, Nigeria’s democratic trajectory can only be strengthened through a cooperative and collaborative executive–legislative relationship.

CONCLUSION/RECOMMENDATIONS

One indisputable fact in democratic practice is that the quality of relationships among political actors largely determines the success or failure of such a system. Nigeria provides a vivid example in this regard. Since its return to democratic rule on May 29, 1999, the country’s political environment has been plagued by constant altercations driven by the unrelenting ambition of political elites to outmaneuver one another in the pursuit and consolidation of power. Consequently, diatribes, mudslinging, and, at times, open confrontation have become recurring features of Nigeria’s political space, particularly among the three arms of government—the executive, legislature, and judiciary—as each strives to assert its independence.

The historical evolution of executive and legislative institutions in Nigeria reveals that these organs were designed to complement one another under the presidential system. However, since 1979, when Nigeria first adopted presidentialism, their relations have often been marked by deadlocks, gridlocks, and stalemates over critical policy issues. The legislature has frequently been unable to perform its constitutional duties effectively due to executive dominance, a trend that resonates not only in Nigeria but also in many other presidential systems globally where executives wield extensive discretionary powers.

Between 1999 and 2015, executive–legislative relations in Nigeria were particularly contentious, marked by persistent crises of confidence. The National Assembly repeatedly threatened impeachment proceedings against the President for non-compliance with legislative enactments, while at the state level, several Houses of Assembly initiated impeachment threats against governors. Some of these threats materialized: Governor Rasheed Ladoja of Oyo State was impeached for refusing to align with President Obasanjo; Governor Peter Obi of Anambra State faced impeachment by his Assembly; while governors in Ekiti and Bayelsa States also suffered similar fates. Yet, many governors survived impeachment attempts by leveraging presidential support, and in turn, orchestrated the removal of Speakers and other legislative leaders. These events produced weakened assemblies with little accountability, transparency, or independence. In some cases, governors even engineered the impeachment of their deputies and Speakers, further undermining legislative credibility.

The persistent conflicts between executives and legislatures at both federal and state levels have had far-reaching negative consequences for governance. Both institutions must recognize their mutual importance in ensuring the smooth functioning of democracy. Unfortunately, systemic corruption has reduced impeachment processes to tools of political vendetta, rather than constitutional accountability. The reluctance of legislators to pursue impeachment against presidents or governors accused of corruption or abuse of office is often politically motivated, thereby perpetuating governance crises.

This unhealthy state of affairs poses grave risks to Nigeria’s democratic stability. At the heart of the friction lies the uneven devolution of power among the three arms of government, with the executive overwhelmingly dominant. Nonetheless, there are emerging signs of progress. For instance, the performance of the legislature in recent years shows a gradual weakening of executive dominance.

Additionally, the general elections of 2011 and 2015 signaled that Nigerians increasingly accept elections as the sole legitimate means of acquiring power, which reinforces accountability and democratic consolidation.

For sustainable democratic governance to thrive, power must be more equitably distributed among the arms of government in order to reduce mistrust, intolerance, and ethnic agitations. The move by the National Assembly to amend the 1999 Constitution to grant financial autonomy to State Houses of Assembly represents a positive step. Such reform, which would charge Assembly funding directly to the Consolidated Revenue Fund, is critical to strengthening legislative independence. To this end, joint sessions of all state assemblies should be convened to sensitize members on the importance of financial autonomy, while ensuring expedited passage of the amendment.

Equally important is the role of political parties in mediating conflicts between their members in the executive and legislature. Parties should develop binding mechanisms for resolving intra-party disputes and sanctioning members whose actions fuel institutional acrimony. However, such mechanisms will only be effective if cross-carpeting (defection) is curtailed. Any legislator who abandons the party platform under which they were elected should be required to vacate their seat and seek re-election, thereby discouraging opportunistic party-switching.

This study demonstrates that both formal constitutional structures and socio-political dynamics have jointly shaped the nature of executive–legislative relations in Nigeria between 1999 and 2015. While the presidential system provides a framework of separation of powers and checks and balances, its effectiveness depends heavily on the wider political, social, and economic environment. Ultimately, both the executive and legislature must view their roles as complementary rather than antagonistic. Despite their institutional separation, neither can function effectively without the other. A cooperative and harmonious relationship, free from excessive executive dominance or legislative docility, is the ideal for consolidating democracy. Thus, Nigeria must foster a new model of executive–legislative relations that transcends president–party or party–government alliances, ensuring governance that truly serves the common good.

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